

The Study of a Pada Varṇa – “Entaninedelupudurā”

Anuthama Murali¹, Dr Rajshri Ramakrishna²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Indian Music, University of Madras ² Associate Professor,
Department of Indian Music, University of Madras

Abstract:

The Saṅgīta-sampradāya-pradarśini (Subbarāma Dīkṣita, 1904) is a documentation of several musical forms, including varṇa-s. Notations for about forty varṇa-s are available in the text, of which twenty-seven are tāna varṇa-s, twelve are cauka and one is a pada varṇa. While the description for cauka and tāna varṇa is given in the saṅgīta-sampradāya-pradarśini, the same is not explicitly given for pada varṇa. The pada varṇa “Entaninedelupudurā” is composed by Subbarāma Dīkṣita in the rāga Kamās and set to tīśra jāti Ēka tāla. The structural organisation of the varṇa, as understood from the notations, seems to be distinct from that of the other varṇa-s in the text and also from description of varṇa given by Subbarāma Dīkṣita in certain aspects. This paper is a study of the structural organisation in pada varṇa “Entaninedelupudurā”. A study of eḍuppu in the caraṇa section in this varṇa is also included in the paper.

Keywords: Entaninedelupudura, pada varna, Subbarama Diksita, Sangita sampradaya pradarsini, eduppu

Varṇa, as a musical form, is seen from the earliest available South Indian publication Saṅgīta-sarvārtha-sāra-saṅgrahamu of Vīṇā Rāmānuja (1859). Early publications are a source of notations of varṇa and other aspects like its classification, structure, composers etc. Notations for more than 150 varṇa-s are seen in early Telugu and Tamil publications¹.

Varṇa-s in early publications are generally classified into tāna, cauka and pada. Svarasthāna varṇa and rāgamālīka varṇa are some types which could be categorised into one

¹ Ramanathan N, “Pre-1940 Music Publications, by N Ramanathan,” *MusicResearchLibrary*, accessed October 4, 2021, <http://www.musicresearchlibrary.net/omeka/items/show/2355>.

of the earlier stated classifications. The classification of cauka, tāna and pada is based mainly on the type of melody in the varṇa, syllabic or mellifluous and the tempo of the varṇa. Other aspects like the organizational structure, mātu (textual content) content, tāla framework may, at times, influence the type of varṇa. But generally, these aspects could be common to any varṇa-type.

Saṅgīta-saṁpradāya-pradarśini (SSP) is an early text in Telugu language, authored by Subbarāma Dīkṣita in the year 1904. This text provides musical notations to several musical forms like gīta, sūlādi, prabandha, kīrtana, sañcāri, padam, svarajati and varṇa. Notation for about 40 varṇa-s are given in the SSP, out of which twenty-seven are tāna varṇa-s, twelve are cauka and one is a pada varṇa. “Entaninedelupudurā” composed by Subbarāma Dīkṣita in Kamās rāga, set to tīsra jāti Ēka tāla is the only pada varṇa in SSP. Also, the SSP is the only source of this varṇa among the early publications. “Varṇasāgaram” (Govindarao, p. 312) is a recent publication with notation for this varṇa.

The organisation of melodic sections in the pada varṇa seems to be distinct, especially in the caraṇa section. The varṇa also incorporates certain attributes relating to the eḍuppu (point of commencement of melody in a tāla) in some sections. This paper is a study of the structural organisation in the pada varṇa “entaninedelupudurā”. A study on the eḍuppu of certain melodic sections and ancillary sections are also included in the study. The description of varṇa given by Subbarāma Dīkṣita in SSP (saṅgīta-lakṣaṇa-saṅgrahamu, p. 50) is studied² and taken into consideration while analysing the related aspects.

² Murali, Anuthama. 2022. “Varṇa-s in Saṅgīta-Saṁpradāya-Pradarśini – With Special Reference to Varṇa-s Composed Prior to Music Trinity.” Traditions of Indian Classical Music and Dance Department of Music, University of Madras, 32–34.

Structural Organisation

The structural organisation of a varṇa is the arrangement of melodic sections which is representative of its presentation. It includes the primary melodic sections like pallavi, anupallavi and caraṇa, and the ancillary sections like muktāyi-svara/ muktāyi-svara-sāhitya and caraṇa-svara/ caraṇa-svara-sāhitya. The number of sāhitya khaṇḍika-s³ in each section, number of āvarta-s, eḍuppu of each melodic section, the repetitions, the refrain, the sequence of singing are other aspects of the structural organisation.

The melodic sections, the sequence of their singing, the khaṇḍika-s to be repeated and refrain lines can be known from the signs and symbols indicated in the varṇa and other compositions in SSP. The structure of the varṇa is given below.

Table 1: Structural organisation of the varṇa “entaninedelupudurā”

<i>Section</i>	<i>Khaṇḍika</i>	<i>Eḍuppu</i>	<i>Āvarta</i>
Pallavi	1	sama	2
	2	½ mātrā	2
Anupallavi	1	sama	2
	2	sama	2
Svarasāhitya		sama	8
Caraṇa	1	1/2 mātra anāgata	4
Svarasāhitya 1		sama	4
	2	sama	
Caraṇa		1/2 mātra anāgata (as refrain)	4

³ A line of sāhitya often demarcated by the presence of prosodical features like prathamākṣara or dviṭīyākṣara prāsa.

<i>Section</i>	<i>Khaṇḍika</i>	<i>Eḍuppu</i>	<i>Āvarta</i>
Svarasāhitya 1		sama	2
Svarasāhitya 2		sama	4
Caraṇa	3	1/2 mātra anāgata	4
Svarasāhitya 1		sama	2
Svarasāhitya 2		sama	4
Caraṇa	4	sama 1/2 mātra anāgata (as refrain)	4
Svarasāhitya 1		sama	2
Svarasāhitya 2		sama	8

The pallavi comprises of two khaṇḍika which is set to four āvarta-s of tīśra jāti Ēka tāla.

Pallavi khaṇḍika 1 - entaninēdelupudurā

Pallavi khaṇḍika 2 - yēlāgu tāludurā

The two khaṇḍika-s are demarcated with the prathamākṣara prāsa in syllables ‘e’ in ‘enta’ and ‘yē’ in ‘yēlāgu’ in the respective khaṇḍika-s. The two khaṇḍika-s of the pallavi are indicated (with the symbol ‘?’) to be repeated twice and then concluded with the sāhitya ‘entaninēdelupudurā’ as indicated by the symbol ‘⊙’. This sāhitya marks the refrain line for the varṇa.

The anupallavi consists of two khaṇḍika-s set to four āvarta-s.

Anupallavi khaṇḍika 1 - mantukekku vīrava

Anupallavi khaṇḍika 2 - santatyāga rājanāsā

Dvītīyākṣara prāsa is observed in the pallavi and anupallavi khaṇḍika-s (syllable ‘ta’ of ‘enta’ and ‘mantu’ in the pallavi and anupallavi respectively). Dvītīyākṣara prāsa is also observed in the two khaṇḍika-s of the anupallavi, also complemented with a dīrgha prathamākṣara⁴. There is no indication of repetition of any khaṇḍika in the Anupallavi.

The svāra-sāhitya is rendered subsequently. This section is set to eight āvarta-s with svāra and corresponding sāhitya passage, svāra passage to be sung first, followed by its corresponding sāhitya. The sāhitya khaṇḍika-s are as follows

sāraguṇa balimiganala

nīrajasumaśaramulana

pāramugatamimigulaga

māruḍu barape śritajana

surasālayikatāḷanura

bālacalamēlakāmāṇ

-taka māṇitaramākan

-tavinumā brahmādinuta

The khaṇḍika-s are marked by prāsa either prathamākṣara or dvītīyākṣara. There is an indication of repeating the first four khaṇḍika-s. The refrain sāhitya ‘entaninēdelupudurā’ ought to be sung once after the svāra and once after the sāhitya of the svāra-sāhitya. Thus, the section concludes with the pallavi.

The caraṇa and caraṇa svāra-sāhitya passages follow the anupallavi section. This varṇa has four caraṇa khaṇḍika-s, each appended with svāra-sāhitya passages.

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-1 - tāpamadhika māyanurā - Dayayūñcuṭaku samayamidirā

⁴ Long syllable as the first syllable of the word.

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-2 - rēpagalī vādērā - lēmabōdhana Vinakārā

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-3 - kōpamēra kavugilīrā - Kōrinavara mulirā

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-4 - śrī puramuna velayumā - Śrītyāga rājasāmī

That the four khaṇḍika-s comprise a single melodic section of the caraṇa can be understood from the dvitīyākṣara prāsa appearing in each khaṇḍika i.e., the syllable ‘pa’ in the commencing words ‘tāpa’, ‘rēpa’, ‘kōpa’ and ‘śrīpu’. The commencing dīrgha akṣara-s ‘tā’, ‘rē’, ‘kō’ and ‘śrī’ in each khandika are also noticed.

It is with respect to the svāra-sāhitya passages appended to the caraṇa khaṇḍika/khaṇḍika-s, that this varṇa differs from the description of a varṇa as given by Subbarāma Dīkṣita. While Subbarāma Dīkṣita describes svāra-sāhitya passages appended to the first caraṇa khaṇḍika alone, the varṇa ‘entaninēdelupudurā’ is composed with svāra-sāhitya passages appended to each of its caraṇa khaṇḍika-s.

The first caraṇa khaṇḍika is appended with one svāra-sāhitya passage, and the last three khaṇḍika-s are appended with 2 svāra-sāhitya passages each. The number of āvarta-s in each svāra sāhitya is recorded in table 1. Every svāra-sāhitya has its respective caraṇa khaṇḍika as the refrain. The primary refrain ‘entaninēdelupudurā’ is rendered at the conclusion of the last svāra-sāhitya of the varṇa (appended to the fourth caraṇa khaṇḍika). As per the description of the sequence of singing in the saṅgīta-lakṣaṇa-saṅgraha, one would normally expect the last caraṇa khaṇḍika to be sung at this stage, followed by the muktāyi svāra, then leading to the pallavi. However, the muktāyi svāra sāhitya is not rendered after singing the last svāra sāhitya or caraṇa khaṇḍika. The varṇa concludes with the pallavi. Elsewhere (Sumitra, p. 174-175) a kīrtana with a similar structure is discussed. The kīrtana ‘karuṇārāsa’ (SSP, p. 815) in Erukulakāmbhōji rāga set to Ādi tala, composed by Kumāra

Eṭṭappa Maharaja is said to have a structure similar to the pada varṇa, with the difference of ancillary svara passages in place of svara-sāhitya passages.

In addition to this aspect, this scholar observes a passage identical to madhyamakāla sāhitya appended to the anupallavi, a feature usually attributed to kīrtana-s. This feature is also observed in the cauka varṇa ‘virakamu’ in the rāga Vamśavati (SSP, Anubandha B, p. 7).

Table 2: Madhyamakāla sāhitya passage in the kīrtana ‘karuṇārasa’ (SSP, p. 815)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
—						==	
s p d ,	s s s r	m , g m	, p , m	p d ś n	d p m p	ds p , m	g r g r
sa ra sī .	ru ha mṛ du	pā.da yu	Gmē.na	sa. rva lō	. Ka śa	. nyē .	śi vē .
					ra	na	Na

Though SSP does not explicitly mention the period of Kumāra Eṭṭappa Maharaja, it is known from his biography (SSP, Vāggēyakāra caritramu, p. 39) that he lived in a period prior to Subbarāma Dīkṣita and that the Maharaja’s son Rāma Venkaṭēsvara Eṭṭappa Maharaja was a senior contemporary of Subbarāma Dīkṣita. It is likely that a similar structural organisation in the caraṇa was earlier incorporated in kīrtana-s.

A note on eḍuppu in the caraṇa section

The pallavi of the varṇa commences on the sama. The eḍuppu is maintained on sama even when the pallavi serves as a refrain line after rendering the anupallavi and at the conclusion of the varṇa. It is earlier seen that the varṇa concludes on the pallavi. The Anupallavi has a sama eḍuppu and are rendered only once in the varṇa.

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-1 and appended svara-sāhitya: The eḍuppu of the caraṇa khaṇḍika-1 has an anāgata eḍuppu marked by ‘P’. The notation of the varṇa is given in the scheme of 6

svara-s in an āvarta of tīśra jāti Ēka, i.e., 2 svara-s per mātrā. In context of the notation scheme, the symbol denotes an anāgata eḍuppu of 1 aksara⁵ or ½ mātrā. It is appended by one svara-sāhitya having a sama eḍuppu, and culminates with the ½ mātrā anāgata eḍuppu of caraṇa khaṇḍika 1.

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-2 and appended svara-sāhitya: The second caraṇa khaṇḍika commences on the sama. There are two svara-sāhitya passages appended to it, having a sama eḍuppu. The first svara sāhitya is set to two āvarta-s. The second svara-sāhitya extends half mātrā or 1 akṣara in excess of 4 āvarta-s, because of which the eḍuppu of the second caraṇa khaṇḍika as refrain, is adjusted accordingly to ½ mātrā anāgata from sama. This adjustment is indicated by the composer by assigning 1 ¼ melodic akṣara-s for the sāhitya syllable ‘rē’ in the caraṇa khaṇḍika-2 when sung as a refrain, instead of 2 ½ akṣara-s when sung with sama eḍuppu. The change in eḍuppu in caraṇa khaṇḍika-2 is illustrated in the table-3 below

Table 3: Caraṇa khaṇḍika-2 with sama eḍuppu

1	2	3	4	5	6
=====		—			
Nśn	d	n d	p	m	,
rē		. pa	ga	li	.

Table 4: Caraṇa khaṇḍika-2 with anāgata eḍuppu

1	2	3	4	5	6
	=====	== _			
	Nśn	dn d	p	m	,
	rē	. pa	ga	li	.

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-3 and appended svara-sāhitya: The eḍuppu of caraṇa khaṇḍika-3 is similar to that seen in khaṇḍika-1 i.e., of ½ mātrā. It is maintained the same when rendered as

⁵ one hrasva melodic unit as per SSP (gamaka-sajnā-vivaraṇamu, p.15)

a temporary refrain for the two svāra-sāhitya-s. There are two svāra-sāhitya passages appended to the caraṇa khaṇḍika-3, which culminate into its anāgata eḍuppu. The eḍuppu of caraṇa khaṇḍika is not seen to change when it serves as the temporary refrain.

Caraṇa khaṇḍika-4 and appended svāra-sāhitya: The fourth and concluding caraṇa khaṇḍika has a sama eḍuppu. However, when it serves as a temporary refrain to the svāra-sāhitya 1 appended to it, the eḍuppu shifts to anāgata eḍuppu of ½ mātrā. This is because, the svāra-sāhitya 1 extends for 2 full āvarta-s and an added ½ mātrā into the third āvarta, because of which the dīrgha melodic svāra (śa) (and its corresponding sāhitya syllable) at the commencement of the caraṇa khaṇḍika-4 is rendered as a hrasva when sung as a refrain. The adjustment of the excess akṣara-s in the caraṇa khaṇḍika is however not indicated in the notations, as done earlier in caraṇa khaṇḍika-2. It is likely that the melodic extension for ‘śa’ on sāhitya akṣara ‘śrī’ is reduced to 1 akṣara from 2, to accommodate for the anāgata eḍuppu. This is illustrated in the table-4 below

Table 5: Caraṇa khaṇḍika-4 with sama eḍuppu

1	2	3	4	5	6
ś	.	ī	ī g	ī	ś ī
śri	.	pu	ra .	mu	na

Table 6: Caraṇa khaṇḍika-4 with anagata eḍuppu

1	2	3	4	5	6
.	ś	ī	ī g	ī	ś ī
.	śri	pu	ra .	mu	na

The second svāra-sāhitya appended to the caraṇa khaṇḍika-4 commences on the sama and culminates into the sama eḍuppu of the pallavi sāhitya ‘entaninedelupurā’.

Thus, it is seen that the eḍuppu of certain khaṇḍika-s in the caraṇa is changed to accommodate the excess units in the svara-sāhitya section appended to it. This feature is earlier seen in the caraṇa khaṇḍika in the varṇa ‘nīsari mannēdora” in Kēdāragauḷa rāga set to Ādi tāla, composed by Kārvēṭinagaram Gōvindasāmayya (SSP, Anubandha B, p 109). The composer of this varṇa is known to have lived before Ādipayya (SSP, Vāggēyakāra caritramu, p. 25). The caraṇa ‘garima’ has an anāgata eḍuppu of 3 mātrā-s. There are six svara-sāhitya passages appended to the caraṇa, of which the concluding passage comprises of colkaṭṭu (jati) syllables interspersed with svara-s. It is observed that every time the caraṇa is rendered as a refrain after the svara-sāhitya/ svara-sāhitya-jati passages, the eḍuppu of the caraṇa khaṇḍika changes from anāgata eḍuppu of 3 mātrā-s to anāgata of 3 ½ mātrā-s. This feature is not seen in later varṇa-s.

Inferences

The Kamās rāga pada varṇa ‘entaninedelupudurā’ is the only pada varṇa in the Saṅgīta-sampradāya-pradarśini. SSP documents many other cauka and tāna varṇa-s. In absence of an explicit description of a pada varṇa by Subbarāma Dīkṣita in SSP, ‘entaninedelupudurā’ seems to incorporate the features of a cauka varṇa with respect to the structure, sequence of singing and melody. While features like the changing eḍuppu of the caraṇa khaṇḍika have been observed in early varṇa-s, it is likely that the feature of svara-sāhitya passages appended to each of the four caraṇa khaṇḍika-s in a varṇa was introduced by Subbarāma Dīkṣita. “Entaninedelupudurā” could serve as a model for the structural possibilities in a varṇa. Subbarāma Dīkṣita has retained the early model of a varṇa concluding with the pallavi.

The observations related to only the structural organisation in the varṇa and the eḍuppu of the melodic sections are noted in this study. A comparative study of pada and cauka varṇa-s in SSP and other publications, with respect to structural organisation could derive further understanding of the form. Study of tāla in ‘entaninedelupudurā’, alongside other varṇa-s set to the same tāla and those set to tāla-s of a similar framework like Rūpaka tāla is another area of study.

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